

Reactions at the Surface of Hot Metallic Filaments.

Part I. The Reaction $\text{CO}_2 + \text{H}_2 \xrightarrow{\text{Pt}} \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{CO}$ on Platinum.

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Prichard and Hinshelwood (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 806) have studied the reaction between carbon dioxide and hydrogen in the presence of a hot platinum wire and have shown that carbon monoxide and water are formed and that the reaction proceeds to completion on absorption of the water. The temperature of the wire was known from its resistance, which according to them was controlled in such a way that the reaction velocities were reproducible to 1 per cent. The data for the reaction-time given by them (*loc. cit.*, p. 808) yield good velocity constants (by the usual unimolecular formula) except for the first value, which is about 25 per cent. in excess of the mean value of the rest. Again a careful examination of the data represented graphically in Figs. 2 and 3 of their paper, shows that their results are not quite so reproducible as they claim. For example in Fig. 2, Curve II of their paper with 100 mm. of each of carbon dioxide and hydrogen at 1000° and after 300 sec., 20 mm. of carbon monoxide are formed, while according to Curve III, 49 mm. of carbon monoxide are obtained and in Fig. 3, Curve II, a similar experiment gives 30 mm. of carbon monoxide. Again in Fig. 3, Curve I, with 50 mm. of hydrogen and 100 mm. of carbon dioxide at 1000° after 300 sec., 25 mm. of carbon monoxide are formed whereas a similar experiment in Fig. 2, Curve II, gives only 10 mm.

It appears therefore, that there is a drift in the activity of the wire and every time an experiment is performed, the condition of the surface is not the same as in the previous instance. Further it is possible that a part of this discrepancy could be attributed to an inefficient method of temperature control.

An attempt has been made in this investigation to secure a more efficient temperature control than the previous workers and the kinetics of the reaction has been studied with the idea of noting the drift in the activity of the wire, due to any change in the surface, during the reactions. The experiments are described in the order

in which they were performed, giving a continuous history of the wire.

The present paper forms a part of an investigation undertaken with the object of studying the effect of various surfaces like platinum, platinum-iridium alloys, tungsten and thoriated tungsten on the interaction of carbon dioxide and hydrogen.

The Apparatus.

The apparatus (Fig. 1) consists of a cylindrical vessel which is closed by a ground glass top and made air-tight by securing with a cement of bees-wax and rosin. The catalyst wire (about 24 cm. long and 0.01 cm. in diameter), directly welded on to stout copper leads, is hung inside the vessel in the form of a U. The bottom of the vessel contains phosphorus pentoxide to absorb the water formed during the reaction and thus cause the reaction to proceed to completion. The connections to the pump and the manometer were all made of capillary tubes.

Fig. 1.

Temperature Control.

Prichard and Hinshelwood (*loc. cit.*) measured the resistance of the hot wire with an ammeter in series and a voltmeter in parallel and from the resistance and the temperature coefficient of the resistance of the wire, they calculated its temperature. They allowed a rough correction of 5 per cent. for the unheated portion of the wire passing through the seal. But it was found in the course of the experiments described here, that the temperature could not be controlled to any degree of accuracy, by an ammeter and a voltmeter alone. The wire was heated by means of a 110-volt battery with a resistance in series. As the reaction proceeded the resistance of the wire increased and the volt and ammeters altered their readings; while the wire was seen to rise from dull red heat to a bright glow.

So the catalyst wire was made one arm of a Wheatstone's bridge and balanced against a known resistance. The ratio of the constant arms was 10:1. By changing the variable arm in a suitable manner the resistance of the wire could be also changed. Volt-ammeter readings were used to calculate the temperature of the wire.

To calculate the temperature of the wire from its resistance, the temperature coefficients of the resistance of the wire between the melting point of ice and the temperature of steam was determined carefully. The resistance of the wire for various currents from 0.05 to 0.175 amp. was measured at the two temperatures, with the aid of a platinum thermometer bridge, with compensating leads of about 1.6 cm. in the circuit, in order to allow for the cooling effect at the leads while the wire was heated. The resistances of the wire for zero current at these temperatures were obtained from the graph (current-resistance) by extrapolation. The following table gives the data for the temperature coefficient of the resistance of three samples of wires used in this investigation.

TABLE I.

Wire.	Temp. coeff. of resistance (α).
No. 1	38.7×10^{-4}
No. 2	37.5×10^{-4}
No. 3	38.3×10^{-4}

Method of Experiment.

Carbon dioxide prepared from pure dry magnesium carbonate and dried over phosphorus pentoxide was collected over mercury in small sampling tubes. Hydrogen was prepared by the electrolysis of a 10 per cent. solution of baryta (Fig. 1). The apparatus was first exhausted and the reaction vessel was immersed in melting ice in an unsilvered Dewar vessel. Carbon dioxide was then let into the apparatus at known pressures from the sampling tubes. Hydrogen from the electrolytic cell was slowly led over a glowing spiral of platinum (to remove the last traces of oxygen) and dried over a long column of phosphorus pentoxide and finally let into the apparatus. Before noting the pressures, the manometer was always adjusted to a constant level. Thus the pressure of each of these gases at constant volume and at 0° was noted. Since the connections to the toppler and the manometer were all made of capillary tubes, the effect of the dead space was negligible especially as the volume of the reaction vessel was above 250 c.c.

The current was switched on for a suitable period, measured by a stop watch. Meanwhile care was taken to balance the bridge. After cutting off the current the wire and the gases were allowed to cool; the water formed was absorbed by the phosphorus pentoxide and the pressure at constant volume was noted. The change in the pressure gave a measure of the reaction velocity. By a repetition of this process the reaction was followed to the end. Thus all the measurements were made at 0° and at constant volume.

In all these experiments it was noticed that the catalyst wire was not steady in activity. It was extremely difficult to get reproducible values at first. After prolonged working the values were fairly reproducible.

Reaction Velocity.

Prichard and Hinshelwood (*loc. cit.*) assume the amount of carbon monoxide formed in the first 300 sec. as a measure of the reaction rate. But it is evident from the results presented here and from their data quoted before that such a procedure is not justifiable. The reaction starts with a high velocity and rapidly falls to a low and steady value. The results are given in the following tables.

With the fresh wire the velocity coefficients calculated on the basis of the usual unimolecular formula, fall off rapidly (Table II). Subsequent experiments show (Tables III and IIIa) that the wire reaches a steady state and unimolecular constants are obtained except for the initial stages. In the next set of experiments (Table IV), the wire was heated to about 1000° in a vacuum for 2 minutes between any two experiments in order to expel any of the adsorbed carbon monoxide. Such a treatment was found to have deactivated the catalyst to a considerable extent. The reaction did not proceed to completion at 1011° but went to about 15 per cent. in 90 sec., and stopped. This 15 per cent. conversion is somewhat like the initial rapid reaction rate. But the wire was able to catalyse the reaction at a higher temperature (Table IV). The results were fairly reproducible after heating the wire in vacuum between experiments.

In Tables III, IIIa, and IV the velocity coefficients are constant after a preliminary period, during which they fall off rapidly.

TABLE II.

Fresh wire No. 1.

Time	Total pressure.	R^*	$(1/c+a)^{**}$
0 sec.	200°0 mm.	—	—
60	164°0	0°00744	900
510	158°0	0°00106	900
1120	153°5	0°000557	900
1500	149°0	0°000474	900
1900	146°0	0°000407	900
2300	142°5	0°000370	910
2700	140°5	0°000334	910
3600	135°5	0°000287	910
4800	130°5	0°000246	—
			Mean 904

* R in this and the following tables represents the velocity coefficients calculated with the usual unimolecular formula.

** The last column in this and other tables $(1/c+a)$ will be explained in the next section dealing with the initial stages of the reaction.

TABLE III.

$P_{\text{CO}_2} = 103 \text{ mm.}$	$P_{\text{H}_2} = 100 \text{ mm.}$	Temp. = 1011°	
Time.	Total pressure.	R.	(1/c + a).
0 sec.	200·0 mm.	—	—
60	192·0	0·00138	98
300	188·0	0·00043	100
900	180·0	0·000254	98
1320	174·5	0·000248	
1920	166·0	0·000216	
2520	158·0	0·000216	
3120	149·5	0·000225	
3720	143·5	0·000224	
4320	138·5	0·000224	

TABLE III a.

0	200·0	—	—
60	195·5	0·000767	102
300	189·0	0·000388	103
600	184·0	0·000290	103
900	179·5	0·000255	104
1320	174·0	0·000228	
1920	166·0	0·000216	
2520	158·0	0·000216	

TABLE IV.

Wire No. 1 heated in vacuum for 2 mins. above 1000°.

$P_{\text{CO}_2} = 100·0 \text{ mm.}$	$P_{\text{H}_2} = 100·0 \text{ mm.}$	Temp. = 1200°.	
0	200·0	—	—
60	177·5	0·00424	102
90	173·0	0·00349	103
120	168·0	0·00321	101
180	158·5	0·00297	100
240	151·0	0·00280	
300	144·0	0·00273	
420	132·0	0·00272	
480	127·0	0·00272	
540	122·0	0·00270	

Initial Stages of the Reaction.

In all the experiments on this reaction with platinum wire, it was noticed that there is an initial part where the reaction rate is high to start with ; it rapidly falls and assumes a steady value. This interesting observation was also noticed and confirmed with two other platinum wires from the same source. First, the possibility of minute traces of oxygen in the carbon dioxide giving rise to the initial rapid rate, was put to a rigorous test. Carbon dioxide was carefully prepared and analysed each time. Since in all the experiments pure carbon dioxide was used, the idea, of small amounts of oxygen giving rise to this effect is completely disproved.

It is possible that this initial fall is due to the rapid poisoning of the catalyst by the carbon monoxide formed in the reaction itself. Experiments were performed at 915° with wire No. 2 in which 100 mm. of carbon monoxide were added to the usual mixture of 100 mm. of carbon dioxide and 100 mm. of hydrogen. The results of two such experiments are given in Fig. 2. The instantaneous rates are plotted against the mean times.

Fig 2.

With a large excess of carbon monoxide—a reaction product—as diluent, the reaction started with a lower velocity than in its absence, rapidly fell to a minimum and seemed to recover

slowly, though it never reached its original value. With 100 mm. each of carbon dioxide and hydrogen at this temperature, the velocity coefficient at the steady stage is 0.0111; but in the presence of 100 mm. of carbon monoxide it started at 0.00049 and fell still lower. It is rather surprising that even if there be carbon monoxide in the system to start with there is still the initial fall in the reaction rate. This seems to suggest that the carbon monoxide formed on the surface in the reaction itself poisons the catalyst.

It is not impossible that of the 'active centres' of the catalyst, some are 'more active' than the rest and hence more susceptible to poisoning. If the adsorbed carbon dioxide and hydrogen, on these 'more active' centres react to form carbon monoxide and water, it is likely that the freshly formed carbon monoxide does not get desorbed from those centres; thus the 'more active centres' are rapidly poisoned by carbon monoxide leaving only a surface less active. This view does not seem to be unlikely when it is known that the heat of desorption of carbon monoxide from a platinum surface is very great and it requires heating of the wire in vacuum at high temperatures of burning with oxygen to remove the adsorbed carbon monoxide (cf. Langmuir, *Trans. Farad. Soc.*, 1922).

The existence of 'more active centres' on the surface appears to be reasonable, for prolonged heating of the wire in vacuum as in the experiments with wire No. 3 (cited later), the initial effect is very nearly eliminated; since it is the more active centres that are easily susceptible to sintering by heat treatment.

On the basis of this idea the initial effect in all these experiments could be accounted for by the equation—

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = \frac{k(a-x)}{1+cx} = \text{Rate of reaction.}$$

Integrating

$$k = \frac{1+ac}{t} \log \frac{a}{a-x} - cx/t$$

where k = velocity constant,
 a = initial pressure of hydrogen,
 x = CO formed in time t .
 c = a constant.

The same equation has been used by Hinshelwood and Prichard (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 327) in their study of the decomposition of nitrous oxide at the surface of platinum where oxygen poisons the catalyst.

In order that this equation may hold good for the initial stages, it is necessary that the graph for $1/t \log a/a-x$ and x/t ought to be a straight line in the initial stages. In all the experiments it is found that this equation gives a straight line for the initial part of the reaction. Some of the graphs are given in Fig. 3, a, b, c, d, & e (K_0 in the graphs stands for $1/t \log a/a-x$). It is interesting that the first experiment with the wire does not give uniform velocity coefficients; but the above equation is seen to be applicable for the entire range of the reaction and all the experimental points lie on a straight line (Fig. 3a) Table II gives the data for the first reaction with wire No. 1 and Table V that for wire No 3.

TABLE V.

 $P_{\text{CO}_2} = 101.9 \text{ mm.}$

Wire No. 3.

 $P_{\text{H}_2} = 102.2 \text{ mm.}$

Temperature = 942°.

Time (sec.).	Total press. (mm.).	$R.$
0	204.1	—
150	176.5	0.00210
300	173.0	0.00121
600	169.0	0.000701
1200	163.0	0.000427
1800	158.4	0.000338
2700	153.2	0.000262
3900	149.0	0.000204
5400	144.1	0.000168
6300	142.3	0.000152

The last column in the Tables II, III and IV refers to the slope of the equation. It is given by $(1/c + a)$.

$$\begin{aligned} k/c &= \left(\frac{1}{c} + a\right) \cdot \frac{1}{t} \log \frac{a}{a-x} - \frac{x}{t} \\ &= \left(\frac{1}{c} + a\right) K_0 - \frac{x}{t} \end{aligned}$$

where K_0 = unimolecular coefficient given by $1/t \log a/(a-x)$

The values for K_0 and x/t are plotted and the value for x/t when $K_0 = 0$ gives the value of K/c ; for if $K_0 = 0$, $K/c = -x/t$, from which by substitution $(1/c + a)$ is calculated.

Even in those experiments with excess of carbon monoxide in the gaseous mixture this equation holds good for the initial stage. For those two experiments the slope of the line for the equation is given in Table VI.

TABLE VI.

Expt. I	...	235	237	230	220
Expt. II	230	229	228
				228	221

Effect of an Inert Diluent on the Reaction.

(With wire No. 1)

Nitrogen has been tried as an inert diluent in the system. Experiments were conducted with 100 mm. of each of carbon dioxide and hydrogen with varying pressures of nitrogen from 100 to 300 mm. at 1200°. The reaction proceeded as usual with the initial peculiarity. The velocity coefficients in the steady stage were the

same as those in the experiments without nitrogen (*cf.* Tables IV and VII). But when about 70 mm. of carbon monoxide had formed in the system the velocity coefficients slowly fall off. This was noted in all the experiments with nitrogen in those cases where there was no nitrogen in the system the reaction rates were all constants even when 70 mm. of carbon monoxide were formed in the system. (*cf.* Table IV).

Fig. 4.

A good example is given in Fig. 4, being an experiment at 915° with wire No. 2. The instantaneous rates are plotted against the mean times. The velocity coefficients in the steady portion is 0.0100 while that of the reaction without nitrogen was 0.011 (experiment not quoted).

TABLE VII.

Wire No. 1 heated in vacuum for 2 mins. at 1000° .

$P_{\text{CO}_2} = 100.6$ mm. $P_{\text{H}_2} = 101.2$ mm. $P_{\text{N}_2} = 101.0$ mm. Temp. = 1200° .

(*N. B.*—For experiment without nitrogen see Table IV).

Time.	Total press.	R
0 sec.	302.7 mm.	0.0137
30	263.4	0.00773
60	265.8	0.00492
120	257.5	
180	247.6	0.00230*
240	239.8	0.00277
300	235.0	0.00285
360	232.0	0.00268
480**	229.0	0.00248

* Calculated from the steady portion of the reaction.

** After this reading the coefficients fall off.

That nitrogen has no effect on the reaction rate is at variance, with the conclusion arrived at by Constable (*Proc. Camb. Phil. Soc.*, 1926, 23, 172) from purely theoretical considerations. The time of stay of an adsorbed molecule on the surface is not dependent on the pressure, for in chemical reactions proceeding at a surface, the adsorbed molecule is released only after its activation. If this activated molecule is evaporated it may be replaced by the reactant or the diluent. From these considerations it is to be concluded that nitrogen is not capable of replacing the reactants from the surface.

The fall in the reaction rate when 70 mm. of carbon monoxide are formed in the presence of nitrogen is peculiar. Perhaps at the later stages when the reactants are small in quantity more of the active surface is left free for the adsorption and the poisoning of it by carbon monoxide. But that this effect is to be noticed only in the presence of nitrogen is difficult to explain. The possibility of experimental errors at the later stages of the reaction is not completely shut out.

Temperature coefficient of the reaction velocity.

(With wire No. 3).

It appears rather difficult to obtain any idea of the temperature coefficient of the reaction velocity for the interaction of carbon dioxide and hydrogen on the surface of platinum, for the activity of the wire changes with use and there is a rapid fall in the velocity coefficients in the initial stages. These difficulties were overcome by carrying out a series of reactions at different temperatures alternately going up and down and heating the wire in vacuum at about 1000° for 5 mins. before each experiment. The behaviour of the wire throughout the operations is interesting and it is enough to mention that such a procedure deactivates the wire. Thus after working 980° and at 1060°, if the reaction was carried out at 980° the activity of the wire was lowered by 50%.

A series of experiments was carried out alternately at higher and lower temperatures with heating of the wire between any two experiments till reproducible values were got. Tables VIII and IX give the results of experiments at 980° and 1060° respectively. The resistance of the wire at 0° after heating in vacuum was found and used in the calculation of these temperatures. It is interesting

to note in passing that heating the wire in vacuum for long periods almost eliminates the initial peculiarity noted with the fresh wire. Perhaps the 'more active centres' are destroyed due to sintering.

TABLE VIII.

Wire heated in vacuum for 5 mins. at about 1000°.

$$P_{\text{CO}_2} = 101.1 \text{ mm. } P_{\text{H}_2} = 102.9 \text{ mm. } \text{Temp.} = 980^\circ.$$

Time.	Total pressure.	Instantaneous rates.
0 sec.	204.0 mm.	—
30	198.5	(0.00183)
60	195.8	0.00111
90	192.0	0.00119
150	187.0	0.00095
300	176.0	0.00091
600	158.2	0.00090
960	144.1	0.00094
1200	132.6	0.00103
1500	124.4	0.00100
		Mean 0.00100

TABLE IX.

Wire heated in vacuum for 5 mins. at about 1000°.

$$P_{\text{CO}_2} = 102.9 \text{ mm. } P_{\text{H}_2} = 101.1 \text{ mm. } \text{Temp.} = 1060^\circ.$$

Time.	Total pressure.	Instantaneous rates.
0	204.0 mm.	—
30	196.2	0.00267
60	189.3	0.00256
90	183.0	0.00252
120	177.1	0.00255
150	171.4	0.00266
180	166.8	0.00232
240	158.9	0.00236
300	152.1	0.00249
360	145.9	0.00229
		Mean 0.00249

Thus the velocity constant rises by about 2.5 times for a rise in temperature of 80° in the neighbourhood of 1000° giving an apparent heat of activation of 38,000 calories, as calculated from Arrhenius' formula (*cf.* Hinshelwood, *loc. cit.*).

Resistance of the wire.

It is possible that as the wire changes its activity with use, the resistance of the wire might also change. But the resistance of the wire while hot did not show much variation. In the course of an experiment the resistance of the hot wire was 12.71 ohms, while that in the next experiment it was 12.76 ohms. The small change of 0.06 ohms even if taken as reliable, gives only a difference of about 10° in the calculated temperatures, which is within the experimental error and is negligible. But the resistance of the wire at the melting point of ice at various stages of the treatment given to it showed appreciable variation, which has to be taken into account in calculating the temperature.

Wire No. 3.

Resistance of the fresh wire at 0°	= 2.7645 ohms.
Resistance of the wire at 0° after two experiments conducted with it at 940°.	= 2.7880
Resistance of the wire at 0° after the experiments in Table IX.	= 2.8465

After

Before

The Surface of the Wire.

The wire was examined under the microscope before and after the experiments. Since the wire under high magnification could not be focussed well, microphotographs could not be taken. But however, parts of the surface of wire were observed through the microscope and the picture of the surface drawn with the aid of a camera lucida.

The surface of the wire (Plate 1) before the experiments appears granular and rough. After the experiments it appears quite smooth and regular; it shows a sintered appearance.

The heating of the wire in vacuum to drive off the adsorbed carbon monoxide, was seen to deactivate it to a decided extent. It shows that the granular parts of the surface which according to Taylor (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1925, **103A**, 105) contain the active centres of the surface, are sintered and thus leaves comparatively less active surface. Such a view seems most probable especially when it is known that a more active catalyst is the one which is more susceptible to poisons and also more sensitive to heat treatment. The reaction with a new piece of wire (*cf.* Tables II and V) is highly retarded by carbon monoxide. Subsequent reactions where the more active centres are held up by carbon monoxide or sintered by heat treatment, proceed with the usual unimolecular velocity without being retarded by carbon monoxide except in the initial stages. Heating it in vacuum for long periods eliminates the initial fall, for the active points on the surface are destroyed. Thus it appears that a rough surface is more active than a smooth one.

This conclusion was confirmed in the following way. The platinum wire No. 3 used in the last experiments was scratched a number of times with fine emery flour spread out on a bit of moist filter paper, thus creating rough surface. The resistance of the wire at the melting point of ice was measured after rubbing it with emery. It was 2.8526 ohms. Table X gives the results of a reaction carried out with the rough wire.

TABLE X.

Wire scratched with emery.

 $P_{\text{CO}_2} = 103.5$ mm. $P_{\text{H}_2} = 101.5$ mm. Temp. = 1040°.

Time.	Total pressure.	Instantaneous rates.
0 sec.	205.0 mm.	—
30	199.3	0.00192*
60	192.5	0.00231
90	185.9	0.00255
120	179.1	0.00287
150	173.0	0.00280
180	167.1	0.00293
210	162.0	0.00278
240	157.0	0.00299
270	151.8	0.00341
300	147.4	0.00318

The temperature of this reaction was calculated with the resistance at 0° found out after scratching the wire with emery. It is noticed that at 1040° (Table X) with the rough wire, the reaction rate is decidedly higher than at 1060° (Table IX) with a smooth wire. Hence the roughness of the surface seems to be a factor of importance in catalysis.

Summary and Conclusions.

1. The interaction between carbon dioxide and hydrogen has been studied at the surface of platinum wire.
2. The fresh wire is poisoned by the carbon monoxide formed on the surface.
3. The reaction is unimolecular except for an initial fall in the reaction velocity which has been shown to be due to the rapid poisoning of the 'more active' centres of the catalyst surface by the carbon monoxide formed thereon.

* The temperature of the wire was on the low side to start with.

4. Heating in vacuum for a long time at high temperatures almost eliminates the initial fall in the reaction rate. The wire is deactivated to a great extent.
5. The resistance of the wire increases on heating in vacuum for a long time.
6. An inert diluent like nitrogen does not affect the reaction rate.
7. The surface of the wire is changed from a granular to a sintered one after the experiments.
8. A rough surface is more active than a smooth or a sintered one.
9. The energy of activation for this reaction at the surface of platinum wire is 38,000 calories.

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